

SABZAVOT DALALARIDA TARQALGAN BEGONA BIOLOGIYASI VA ULARGA QARSHI KURASH

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ANNOTATSIYA

Maqolada sabzavot dalalarida tarqalgan begona o'tlarga qarshi kurashishda, Pivot 10% s.e.k, Zenkor ultra gerbitsidlarini qo'llashning samaradorligi bo'yicha olingan tadqiqot natijalari keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: sabzi, piyoz, pomidor, gerbitsid.

KIRISH

Bugungi kunda dunyoda aholining oziq-ovqat mahsulotlariga bo'lgan ehtiyojini qondirishda kartoshka va sabzavot ekinlarining yalpi hosili va hosil sifatini oshirish muhim ahamiyat kasb etmoqda. Sabzavot va poliz mahsulotlarini yetishtirish bo'yicha Xitoy (202-205 mln.t.) birinchi o'rinda turadi. Sabzavotchilik rivojlangan mamlakatlar Hindiston (68-75 mln. t), AQSh (34-36 mln. t.), Turkiya (17-21 mln. t), Italiya (12-15mln.t.), Rossiya (11,5-14,2 mln. t.), Yaponiya (11-13 mln. t.) va h.k. Aholi jon boshiga yiliga sabzavotlar yetishtirish Xitoyda 250-270, Italiyada 230-250, Polshada 150-160, AQShda 130-145, Yaponiyada 120-140, Ukrainada 90-100, Rossiyada 86-94 kilogrammni tashkil etadi. Lekin, sabzavotlar yalpi hosilining 10-20 % i begona o'tlar tufayli yo'qotilmoqda. Dunyo dehqonchiligida 3000 dan ortiq turdagi begona o'tlar tarqalgan va 40 dan ortiq turi katta zarar keltiradi. Ularga qarshi agrotexnik va kimyoviy kurash choralarini uyg'unlashgan holda qo'llab AQSh, Xitoy, Germaniya, Rossiya, Avstraliya, Janubiy Koreya, Hindiston, va boshqa mamlakatlarda yuqori natijalarga erishilgan.

TADQIQOTNING MAQSADI

Toshkent viloyatining sug'oriladigan tipik bo'z tuproqlari sharoitida begona o'tlar va gulli parazitlarning turlari, sabzavot ekinlari maydonlarida tarqalishi hamda keltiradigan zararini hozirgi kundagi ahvolini aniqlash va ularga qarshi kurash choralarini ilmiy jihatdan asoslab berishdan iborat.

TADQIQOTNING VAZIFALARI

begona o‘tlar va gulli parazitlarini turlarining qishloq xo‘jalik ekin dalalarida tarqalishining hozirgi ahvolini tadqiq qilish;

sabzavot vakartoshka ekinlari dalalarida tarqalgan begona o‘tlar va gulli parazitlarning zararini o‘rganish;

begona o‘tlar va gulli parazitlarning urug‘larini unib chiqishi va bu jarayonga ta’sir qiluvchi omillarni o‘rganish;

sabzavot va kartoshka ekinlari dalalarida keng tarqalgan begona o‘tlar va gulli parazitlarga qarshi kurash choralarini asoslab berish;

begona o‘t va gulli parazitlarga qarshi tavsiya etilgan kurash choralarining iqtisodiy samaradorligini baholash.

Tadqiqotning ob’ekti sifatida Toshkent viloyatining yuqori, o‘rta, quyi qismidagi tipik bo‘z tuproqlar, begona o‘tlar va gulli parazitlar, pomidor, piyoz va sabzi ekinlari, pivot 10% s.e.k, zenkor ultra gerbitsidlari olingan.

TADQIQOT NATIJALARI

Toshkent viloyati sharoitida sabzavot ekinzorlarida avtotrof begona o‘tlarning 28 ta turi hisobga olindi. Ularning 20 ta turi bir yillik, 2 ta turi ikki yillik va 6 ta turi ko‘p yillik begona o‘tlar ekanligi aniqlandi. Toshkent viloyati sharoitida zarpechaklar parazitlik qilgan 75 ta turga mansub qishloq xo‘jaligi ekinlari va manzarali o‘simliklarda eng ko‘p tarqalgan turlar *C.lehmanniana* (52 turda), *C. breviflora* (50 turda). va *C.monogyna* (33 turda), kam tarqalgani *C.appoximata* (1 ta turda), *C.chinensis* (7 turda), *C.epilinum* (9 turda), va *C.campestri* (12 turda) ekanligi aniqlandi. Zarpechak urug‘lari unuvchanligini uzoq muddat saqlab, qulay sharoit kelganda unib chiqishi, uzoq davom etgan past harorat ta’siri va tuproq chuqurligining oshib borishi zarpechak urug‘larining unuvchanligini pasaytirishi qayd etildi. Zarpechak urug‘larini suvda qolib ketishi ularning unuvchanliga deyarli ta’sir etmasligi, besh oy davomida suvda saqlangan zarpechak urug‘larining unuvchanligi 73,0–92,0 foizni tashkil etishi aniqlandi. Pivot 10 % s.e.k. gerbitsidini piyoz, sabzida uchraydigan zarpechak turlariga qarshi eng yaxshi natija 1,0 l/ga me’yorda qo‘llanilganda qayd qilinib, bunda biologik samaradorlik nazoratga nisbatan kartoshkada 92,3 %, piyozda 89,1 % va sabzida 93,7 % bo‘lganligi aniqlandi. Pivot 10 % s.e.k 1,0 l/ga me’yorda qo‘llanilganda nazoratga nisbatan hosildorlik piyozda 43,6 %, sabzida 37,2 % yuqori bo‘ldi. Pivot 10 % s.e.k. gerbitsidini sabzavot o‘simliklarida parazitlik qiluvchi zarpechaklarga qarshi ishlatilganda rentabellik darajasi piyozda 194,5 % va 1915500 so‘m, sabzida 225,6 % va 4365500 so‘m bo‘lishi aniqlandi. Pomidor dalalaridagi begona o‘tlarga qarshi Zenkor ultra gerbitsidi 0,8 va 1,0 l/ga me’yorlarda qo‘llanilganda apreldan–avgustgacha biologik samaradorlik mos ravishda 83,4–90,1 va 85,9–91,8 foizni tashkil etgan. Zenkor ultra gerbitsidi 0,8 l/ga me’yorda

ishlatilgan variantda nazorat variantiga nisbatan 52,0 s/ga, 1,0 l/ga me'yorda qo'llanilganda 54,0 s/ga qo'shimcha pomidor hosili olindi.

XULOSA

Toshkent viloyatining tipik bo'z tuproqlari sharoitida tarqalgan begona o'tlarga qarshi kurash tadbirlarining samaradorligini aniqlash bo'yicha olib borilgan ilmiy tadqiqotlarning natijalari asosida:

sug'oriladigan maydonlarda zarpechak tarqalishini kamaytirish uchun zarpechak urug'ini tarqatuvchi manbalarda (sug'orish tarmoqlarining qirg'oqlari, dala chetlari) o'sadigan turli begona o'tlarga qarshi muntazam kurash olib borish, zarpechak urug'larini yo'qotish uchun zararlangan o'simlik qoldiqlarini daladan tashqariga chiqarib o'raga tashlash, yoqib yuborish va ko'mish, hamda shu joylarda tuproqni chuqur shudgor qilish; piyoz va sabzi dalalarida uchraydigan zarpechak turlariga qarshi Pivot 10 % s.e.k. gerbitsidini 0,3 % foizli konsentratsiyada 1,0 l/ga me'yorda ekinlarni ekish davrida qo'llash; pomidor dalalaridagi bir yillik begona o'tlarga qarshi Zenkor ultra preparatini pomidor ko'chatlari ekilgandan so'ng tasma usulida 0,8 l/ga me'yorda qo'llash tavsiya etiladi.

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